

THE ROLE OF IDEOLOGICAL FACTORS IN ENSURING SECURITY

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the fact that the diversity of ideas in social development and its democratic character is directly related to the human factor and its activity, and that the struggle between good and evil ideas is a legacy of mankind from history.*

Keywords: *diversity of ideologies, democratic values, mutual contradictions between societies.*

If we look at history, the foundation stone of the emergence of ideas corresponds to the period of ancient civilizations. It is the influence of nature on society or the influence of customs and traditions in society that creates the desire to live. Under its influence, new and new ideas appear through the human mind and thinking. These ideas can be both good and bad at the same time.

Therefore, it is impossible to understand and explain the internal conflicts of the development of society and the development of human spiritual maturity without taking into account the ideas and ideologies that influence them. For this reason, great people in all times paid great attention to the study of the ideological and ideological foundations of society, sought new opportunities for development, and sought to create advanced ideas.

The experience and development of social life during the years of independence showed that people and society cannot live without ideas and ideology. After all, man always feels the need for a life-giving idea that motivates him to constant activity. There is no void in the human heart and mind, just as there is no void in nature and society. If the healthy idea is not the priority in the life of the society, the hearts and minds of the people will be taken over by harmful ideas and they will ruin the way of life of the people. Just as the wealth of the world is a struggle between different forces, the goal of capturing the hearts and minds of people and turning them into weapons in their hands is clearly manifested through the action of various aggressive currents.

Positive influence of creative ideas and ideologies in the life of society. The power that preserves humanity from all kinds of destruction is goodness. Virtue is the cornerstone of the emergence, formation and development of creative ideas and ideologies. Not everyone is born brave or cowardly, generous or stingy, honest or thieving, hardworking or lazy, friend or enemy, rich or poor, loyal or treacherous, loyal or unfaithful. He is born as an ordinary human child from his mother. Positive or negative characteristics and qualities of a person are formed and developed

during his life as a result of the upbringing he received in the family, school, neighborhood, workplace, and the influence of the spiritual and moral environment in society.

Since the beginning of humanity, two forces - goodness and evil - have been constantly fighting each other in its spiritual body. Goodness encourages people to live peacefully, and evil encourages them to do evil deeds. It is not surprising that the good - constructive ideas and ideologies, and the evil - destructive, destructive ideas and ideologies in the ways of this struggle, which has been going on for centuries, have been born. After all, the history of humanity consists not only of the history of wars and riots between people and nations on the battlefields, but also of the history of struggles between ideas.

The historical forms and content of ideas and ideologies have always been determined by the dialectic of the struggle between good and evil, creativity and destruction, that is, in contrast to the ideologies of invasion, getting rich at the expense of others, aggression, and fanaticism, the ideas of freedom, independence and justice have been constantly emerging. , has become the victorious flag of nations.

Creative ideas that glorify man and society, increase his energy and potential, and mobilize him to do useful things for his people, the Motherland, and the whole of humanity, embody noble goals such as work, development, friendship, freedom, independence, peace, justice, and honesty. is said to the idea.

Features of the manifestation of creative ideas:

- encourages the people to work together towards a noble goal, leads to progress;
- expresses the hopes and goals of every nation, glorifies free life and a fair system;
- increases human dignity in every way, increases the well-being of the people;
- a moral criterion that determines the extent to which each person fulfills his duty to society, country, nation, himself and his family;
- as an ideological way of thinking, finds solutions to problems arising in society;
- correctly analyzes events, evaluates them, makes logical conclusions.

Creative ideas are distinguished by their noble goals of making the country prosperous and people's lives prosperous. They have been living as the noblest ideals of the life of the society since the time when mankind reached civilization. The meaning of these eternal ideas is also reflected in the words of our President, Supreme Commander of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "Our nation is historically capable of great deeds." Such creativity has been inherited by our people from their ancestors.

The idea of national statehood and its positive impact on the development of nations can be clearly seen in the case of the new Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan's policy of international cooperation, regional peace, inter-ethnic harmony serves as a basis for the rule of stability.

Scientific discoveries also greatly influence the development of ideology. Advances in modern science, such as cosmonautics, cybernetics, nanotechnology, great discoveries such as determining the genetic map of a person, are dramatically changing people's imagination.

At the same time, high scientific and technical progress, processes of globalization, on the one hand, increase confidence in the possibilities of human intelligence and the future, on the other hand, they also cause universal problems such as the tragedies of Hiroshima, Nagasaki, Chernobyl, weapons of mass destruction, ecological disasters, spiritual decline. .

Therefore, the society needs a healthy idea and a healthy ideology for the rational use of scientific and cultural achievements.

If philosophy and ideology do not reflect the principles of humanism and development, the need for progress in the destiny of the people, on the contrary, if it rejects these aspirations, in essence, contradicts them, it causes the decline of society.

One of these ideologies is the ideology of the former communist regime, which seized power by force of arms. This ideology, which prevailed in the territory of a huge kingdom and a socialist camp, which occupied one sixth of the world, fell into decline due to its inhuman and non-national essence and authoritarian nature.

The realities of life show that sometimes destructive ideas can poison the public mind with their false charm, deception and trickery and take a dominant position in society. For example, the victory of fascism in Italy and Germany in the 30s of the 20th century brought immense hardship not only to the Italian and German people, but also to millions of people around the world. However, these ideas began to appear in these countries from the beginning of the century. For example, in Italy, since 1910, the magazine "National Idea" began to be published, in which aggressive nationalism was promoted. The rise of Nazism to power in Germany in the early 1930s led to the outbreak of World War II. Unfortunately, because it was not abolished in its time, it became a temporary dominant idea and caused millions of victims.

Today, progressive and humanist forces around the world are working together to prevent such tragic and unpleasant situations from happening again. In the words of Islam Karimov, since time immemorial, mankind has been struggling with idea against idea, thought against thought, and enlightenment against ignorance - this is an unchanging law of history.

The negative impact of destructive ideas and ideologies on the life of society. As long as people and society exist, tyranny and violence, arrogance and ignorance, which are contrary to good ideas, try to manifest in new forms. But they cannot stop people from striving towards higher goals based on the ideas of justice, peace and brotherhood, development and prosperity.

Dissatisfaction of people with reality: envy, anger, impatience, intolerance, panic, fear, invisibility, betrayal, etc. lead them to evil behavior: slander, gossip, lying, espionage, violence, threats, aggression. In the world, the mechanisms of implementation of destructive ideas and ideologies are being developed and launched across ideological fields by individuals, public organizations, and even states who support these actions.

Destructive ideas are ideas that use various effective means to push people and society to false and evil goals, condemn nations and states to decline and destruction, channel their power into corruption and crime, and bring only trouble for humanity.

Characteristics of disruptive ideas:

- striving for ideological autonomy;
- rejection of pluralism of opinions;
- non-recognition of democratic and national values;
- claiming absolute power;
- tendency to socio-political instability in the society;
- establishment of a single, dominant ideology;
- use of social conflicts;
- such as supporting fanaticism and political extremism.

Harmful consequences of destructive ideas: it changes the way of thinking of a person in a negative way, forms an unhealthy lifestyle, promotes foreign customs and traditions, restricts the

diversity of thoughts, alienates the people from their own path of development, undermines inter-ethnic harmony and inter-religious tolerance in society, and causes internal conflicts. emits

The main purpose of the destructive ideas is that people who are vengeful for money and position, some countries striving for hegemony, take possession of the material wealth of other peoples by using methods such as coercion or deceit, false praise or discrimination, and as a result, they serve to turn oppressed peoples into free labor.

Tasks of destructive ideas: to derail the country's economic system by secretly collecting and using information about the material and spiritual wealth of other nations by spies hired on the instructions of certain political forces, organizations and states, that is, by falsifying the history of nations, separating them from their identity, national values discrimination, discrediting the heads of state offices by spreading all sorts of fabrications about senior officials and their family members, finding those who are dissatisfied with the state policy and inciting them to betray their country, urging people to overthrow the state power under the pretext of democracy.

It is extremely important to know the essence and purpose of destructive ideas. After all, for military personnel, awareness of the danger of destructive ideas is a factor in creating ideological immunity and acquiring the necessary knowledge.

Destructive ideologies and destructive actions are based on inhumane ideas, they teach people to look at human beings and the achievements of mankind with hatred, they encourage destruction.

Forms of destructive ideology:

Extremism (lat. ultra) is a theory and practice that advocates extreme ideas and measures in solving problems of a socio-political nature. According to the content - religious and secular. Forms of appearance - territorial, regional, international. Extremist views never knew borders, did not recognize religion, nation, or territory. Secular extremism has developed in political, economic, ideological forms, and religious extremism has developed under the guise of all religions.

Whatever the name or form of extremism, its primary goal is to gain power by forming, arming and mobilizing militant groups.

Religious extremism is a set of extreme actions and views carried out by fanatics or groups acting according to their will in the pursuit of certain political goals and under the guise of religion. No matter where and under which religion they operate, their goal is to establish a religious state, and they aim to achieve this goal through conflicts, conflicts, armed conflicts, that is, bloodshed and violence. This will be a big blow to both independence and development.

Religious fanaticism (French: prayer) is a religious bigotry (hardly given to religion, extremely devoted), a harmful trend that considers only certain rules to be superior in life, strives to make the truth about God its own, does not recognize progress, superstition, and blasphemes any innovation.

The term fundamentalism was coined in connection with the Christian religion. Fundamentalists promoted the idea of promoting the basic principles of the Christian religion and introducing the rules of religious life of that time, and it includes five doctrines: the birth of Jesus from a virgin woman, his sacrifice to atone for the sins of mankind, his physical resurrection, his second physical appearance on Earth. coming, sanctifying the book and restoring it to its original purity.

Orientations in different religions prefer not to change the beliefs stated in the holy books, to follow the religious rules without words.

Islamic fundamentalism propagates the false views that it is necessary to disguise Islam and return to the pure basis of Islam, to practice Islam in its original form, and only in this way can Islam be "cleansed" of heresies. They are trying to achieve their goals through force, violence, bloodshed, even armed struggle.

Two characteristics of Islamic extremism:

- it seems that all modern Muslim communities have lost their Islamic colors and have become Jahiliyyah (pre-Islamic) age societies. Such an approach serves as a "basis" for criticizing the government and its policies;

- they are supposed to be "real" Muslims, that is, they believe that once they come to power, it is necessary to take drastic and aggressive action to establish the future "Islamic order".

Currents and trends in different religions prefer not to change the beliefs stated in the holy books, to follow the religious rules without words.

In fact, the purpose of the ideas of "fundamentalism" and "extremism" to enter Central Asia is not to restore religious values, but to use these ideas as a tool to create instability, religious and ethnic conflicts in the region, and ultimately to gain power.

So, today, we should fully realize our children's not only material, but also spiritual and educational potential.

I think there is a need to develop a law "On the procedure and principles of teaching social sciences in the continuing education system" and put it into practice.

In this regard, it is appropriate to create and implement the "Strategy of Humanization of the Continuous Education and Training Sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2030".

As the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, noted about this: "There will never be such a thing as a vacuum in the field of ideology. Because a person's heart, brain, and mind never stop receiving information, thinking, and being influenced. Therefore, he always needs spiritual food. Tell me, what will happen if he does not get this food from the environment in which he lives, or if this environment does not satisfy him? He gradually looks for such food elsewhere. We should not allow this" [1].

In the following years, great work is being done in our country to improve the spiritual and educational environment in schools, to increase the reputation and prestige of the teaching profession, to educate new era pedagogues, to develop the science of pedagogy, and to introduce innovative educational technologies. The head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted 6 decrees and decisions on the public education system, 21 decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers, and the legal and regulatory foundations of reforms in this field were strengthened. Legal equality is a noble value that is important not only for the provision of human rights, but also for the political, socio-economic development of society. In addition, legal equality is one of the indicators showing the level of democratic development of the country [2]. It is precisely in the conditions of today's globalization that attention is paid to this issue as a priority issue in our society.

Ensuring the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work" dated May 3, 2019 No. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1059 of December 31, 2019, the "Concept of Continuous Spiritual Education" was adopted. According to this concept, effective implementation of the tasks related to the education

of the population, especially the youth, provided for in the Action Strategy on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, providing them with the most necessary basic competencies for a peaceful life, spiritual development of scientifically based indicators for the assessment of upbringing, based on the principles of continuity and coherence in the upbringing process, first of all, the correct organization of the mother's pregnancy period, and the determination of the main directions for the spiritual upbringing of babies and children were shown. Now, the duration of this process is included in the seven priorities of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

Also, it is important to gradually form such important qualities as loyalty to the Motherland, entrepreneurship, willpower, ideological immunity, kindness, responsibility, tolerance, legal culture, innovative thinking, and hard work in young people, starting from childhood. In particular, to develop and implement a mechanism of mutual effective cooperation of parents, caregivers, teachers, continuing education institutions and the neighborhood community in the implementation of continuous spiritual education of a woman from the period of pregnancy to the age of 30, to increase the knowledge of the population on child rearing. , the main task is to increase the pedagogical culture, to regularly acquaint citizens with effective pedagogical technologies, methods and forms of implementation tested in the world experience of continuous spiritual education. At the same time, state organizations, civil society institutions are responsible for forming a healthy worldview and organizing continuous spiritual education against malicious information, vices that erode morals, and destructive ideas that lead young people astray through mass media, including the Internet - the global information network. , effective establishment of cooperation between the mass media and the private sector was established.

Today, Uzbekistan is entering a new stage of development based on the principle of "From national recovery to national growth". As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted while thinking about this: "Today, the phrase "New Uzbekistan" is mentioned when talking about our country on a global scale. This is a recognition that we have stepped into a completely new stage of development in recent years, and that we are making great progress" [3]. After all, the intensity of the new era is putting its clear, strict and consistent demands on the education system. Within the framework of these requirements, the material and moral conditions of pedagogues in the field of education are radically improved, and modern technologies for improving the quality of education are being introduced.

It is known from the worldly development that upbringing and education cannot be separated from each other, these two processes are harmonious, organized on a continuous basis only when they are polite, have moral qualities, high spirituality, and at the same time are knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy. , educates patriotic young people with a broad worldview and thinking, possessing a modern profession. Precisely, these factors, the work being carried out on the scientific and technological reform of youth education in Uzbekistan on a modern basis require its formation on the basis of scientifically based basic competencies and qualities based on the needs of today [4, p.5-9].

At the moment, a suitable response to the fierce competition that is taking a sharp turn on the world scale only through the wide introduction of modern science and innovation achievements is becoming a priority in our activities as a strategic task. In this regard, we ensure that the youth of our country boldly enter independent life by forming loyalty to the Motherland, duty and responsibility, initiative and other qualities. It is no secret that some young men and women face

a number of problems in finding their place in life. For example, the lack of formation of high goals in some students, insufficient development of self-motivation, will, perseverance, diligence, and action qualities also harms the quality of education. can be observed showing.

In the field of spiritual education, it is sometimes shown that there are insufficient educational materials, including methodical manuals related to the field of ideological education, necessary textbooks for students, which provide a methodical basis for teachers' activities. Further development of the system of spiritual education through the successful implementation of the concept of "Continuous spiritual education" is of particular importance in preventing and eliminating these shortcomings.

At the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly in 2017, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev proposed the development of the UN International Convention on Youth Rights and the adoption of a special UN General Assembly resolution entitled "Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance". In the fight against corruption, we will not be able to achieve the high goals that are ahead of us unless all members of the society are vaccinated with the "honesty vaccine".

An anti-corruption agency was established, accountable to the Parliament and the President.

Persons who arrived and settled in Uzbekistan before 1995 are granted automatic citizenship.

The prime minister, all members of the government, regional governors report to the parliament, leaders of regions and districts report on their activities to local councils.

The Public Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established in order to further strengthen public control and establish close cooperation between the state and society.

Priorities in the field of security, international harmony and religious tolerance, as well as a well-thought-out, mutually beneficial and practical foreign policy.

Priority directions in the field of ensuring security, religious tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony:

- Protection of the constitutional system, sovereignty, territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- ensuring information security and improving the information protection system, providing timely and appropriate resistance to threats in the information field;

- strengthening civil, inter-ethnic and inter-confessional peace and harmony;

- strengthening the state's defense capabilities, increasing the combat power and potential of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- prevention of environmental problems that harm the natural environment, public health and gene pool;

- improvement of the emergency situation prevention and elimination system.

Priorities in the field of thoughtful, mutually beneficial and practical foreign policy:

- strengthening the independence and sovereignty of the state, increasing the place and role of the country as an equal subject of international relations, entering the ranks of developed democratic states, creating an environment of security, stability and harmonious neighborhood around Uzbekistan;

- to strengthen the international reputation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to provide unbiased information to the world community about the reforms being carried out in the country;

- improvement of the legal framework of the foreign political and economic activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the contractual and legal basis of international cooperation;
- solving the issues of delimitation and demarcation of the state border.

This direction plays an important role in the further development of our country and the peaceful life of our compatriots.

In order to strengthen the atmosphere of inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance in the society, "Friendship Week" and "Dostlik" international forum-festival were held on July 30 - "International Friendship Day" [5, p.43-45].

In conclusion, the sense of patriotism is strengthened by understanding, feeling and understanding family and children's upbringing. That is why we believe that it is necessary to teach a subject related to the military field once a week in three stages of continuous education. These are in schools, secondary and higher educational institutions...

The essence of the large-scale reforms implemented under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev calls people to understand and feel the human factor in life and internal possibilities more deeply, and not to shy away from work. The spiritual and physical maturity of citizens, especially the youth of the country, calls for a sense of high civic responsibility through the idea of the development of the Motherland, the peace of the country and the well-being of the people.

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